

VARIATION OF VAPOUR PRESSURE OF SUPERSATURATED SOLUTIONS WITH TEMPERATURE. PART I

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The vapour pressure of several systems of electrolytes and non-electrolytes in water has been investigated at various temperatures. It has been shown that Clausius-Clapeyron equation is applicable even in supersaturated solutions. The deviations can be explained on the basis of Ravinovitch's solvate hypothesis. It has been shown that no break occurs at the supersaturated region. Latent heat of evaporation of solution has also been calculated.

Freezing point (De Coppet, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1871, *iv*, 23, 366), electrical conductivity (Hein, *Ann. Physik*, 1886, 27, 643), specific viscosity (Nicol, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1887, 51, 381; Taimni, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 32, 604), specific gravity and other thermal properties vary gradually, and no abrupt change occurs when the system passes from the saturated to the supersaturated region. So far no attempt has been made in this direction to study the vapour pressure of supersaturated solutions. In the present communication an attempt has been made in this direction.

The present investigations also afforded an opportunity to study the applicability of Clausius-Clapeyron equation to concentrated and supersaturated solutions. Many workers have applied the equation

$$\frac{d \ln p}{dT} = \frac{L_s'}{RT^2} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

to pure liquids and melts. In the case of solutions, the equation takes the form

$$\frac{d \ln p}{dT} = \frac{L_s}{RT^2} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where L_s = latent heat of evaporation from solution.

Integrating the above equation, we have

$$\ln p = -\frac{L_s}{RT} + C \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

(assuming that L_s does not change much within a small range of temperature).

Putting $\frac{L_s}{R} = D,$

we get $\ln p = -\frac{D}{T} + C.$

Here the applicability of the above equation has been tested.

EXPERIMENTAL

Of all the methods for determining vapour pressure, the dewpoint method developed by Lescoeur (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1889, *vi*, 16, 378; 1890, 19, 533) and improved by Cum-

ming (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 1772) was found to be most suitable for the study of vapour pressure of supersaturated solutions. The fact that the supersaturated solution is to be left undisturbed limits the applicability of other methods in such cases. In static method significant errors are introduced through the failure to remove completely minute traces of air or other volatile impurities dissolved in the liquid or absorbed on the walls of the containing vessel, while in the dewpoint method, presence of traces of air is immaterial. Similarly, in the air-saturation methods difficulties are encountered in handling and measuring large volumes of inert gases which must be employed in order to evaporate an accurately weighable quantity of the liquid. One other additional advantage of the dewpoint method is that the equilibrium between the solution and saturated vapour is attained within half an hour. The method has been applied by McBain and Salmon (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 429) for determining the molecular weight of salts of fatty acids in solutions. Several modifications were made by Hipburn (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1928, A, 40, 255). Recently the principle has been employed by Puck and Wise (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1946, 50, 329) for the determination of vapour pressure of liquids.

The apparatus consisted of spherical bulb of 100 c.c. capacity resembling that of McBain and Salmon (*loc. cit.*) in other respects. Suitable volatile liquids e. g., ether, acetone and alcohol were put in the silver tube. The whole apparatus was put in a specially constructed air thermostat having a glass pane which facilitated the observation of the temperature of appearance and disappearance of dew. The dewpoint was determined in exactly the same way as McBain and Salmon (*loc. cit.*) did. The vapour pressure of the saturated vapour at the dewpoint at the temperature of thermostat was found out from International Critical Tables.

From the above observations the latent heat of evaporation has been calculated by using the integrated form of the equation (1) between two specific temperatures.

TABLE I

No.	Substance.	Conc. per 100 g. of water.	Temp. range.	L_v (cal./g. mol.)	C.
1	NH ₄ Cl	41.4	35-45°	10,650	8.9927
2	NH ₄ NO ₃	250.0	35-45°	10,210	8.4753
3	NH ₄ Br	95.1	35-45°	9,910	8.5804
4	KCl	32.5	20-30°	10,000	8.5701
5	KBr	70.6	30-40°	10,370	8.8532
6	KI	156.0	30-40°	10,310	8.7252
7	KCNS	265.1	30-40°	10,483	8.6886
8	Urea	166.6	35-45°	10,530	8.8351
9	Resorcinol	225.0	30-40°	11,145	9.2918
10	Tartaric acid	185.0	35-45°	11,610	9.5361
11	NaNO ₃	94.9	35-45°	11,170	9.2100
12	CH ₃ COONa	136.0	35-45°	12,590	10.2528

DISCUSSION

From the results given above, vapour pressure-temperature and log vapour pressure ($\log p/T$) curves have been drawn. It is revealed from the graphs, that no abrupt

change in the vapour pressure-temperature curve occurs as the supersaturated region is approached. This further confirms the deductions based on the study of viscosity, freezing point and electrical conductivity data. With only one or two exceptions, the curve $(\log p - 1/T)$ is a straight line. Hence, it appears that Clausius-Clapeyron equation is fairly applicable to these systems. The apparent anomaly in the case of sodium acetate may be due to its tendency to form several hydrates. Similar sort of behaviour is exhibited in $(\log \eta - 1/T)$ curves (Ram Gopal, Ph. D. thesis, 1946, Lucknow University).

In Table I the latent heats of evaporation from solutions and the constant C have been calculated. The value of the constant C is almost the same in every case. The values of the latent heat of evaporation can be divided in two categories

(a) Above 10,450 cal./g. mol. (b) Below 10,450 cal./g. mol.

Substances of category (a) show a marked tendency of forming solvates. Greater solvation will require greater shearing stress, and hence latent heat of evaporation will be greater than that in other cases. This tendency of forming hydrates is responsible for the departure from linearity in the above case. Thus, the departure is most marked in the case of sodium acetate, which has the highest tendency of forming solvates and consequently the highest latent heat of evaporation should be observed in this case. The lower values in category (b) may be due to depolymerisation of water molecules.

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THE RATE OF CRYSTAL GROWTH IN SUPERSATURATED SOLUTIONS. PART I

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The rate of crystal growth in supersaturated aqueous solutions of four substances have been measured at different temperatures. It is found that there exists a temperature at which the rate of growth is maximum.

The rate of crystal growth in melts has been studied by Tamman and his co-workers in detail (Tamman, "Kristallisieren und Schmelzen", p. 131). Walton and his co-workers have studied the speed of crystallisation of water and the effect of dissolved substances on this speed (Walton and Brann, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 317; 1918, 40, 1168). It has been observed by these workers that for under-cooled melts, the rate of crystal growth increases with the degree of supercooling until at a certain temperature it reaches a maximum. On cooling further, the rate of crystal growth again decreases. It appears from a survey of literature that very little work has been done